

WHAT EFFECTIVELY REPRESENTS THE ACT OF READING?

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7295302

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of the act of reading, from the perspective of scientifically discussing 'what does the act of reading actually represent? their symbolic representations. Its social relevance is based on the principle of clarifying to the population, in general, that the act of reading is something that, in addition to promoting the elucidation of the individual, allowing them to become more aware of their rights and duties, can open up to them a range of opportunities. This is an opinion article, based on classic authors, characterized as a bibliographic research, which seeks to explore various aspects of the subject, from the perspective of other sciences. It uses dialectical materialism as an investigative principle, believing that this method is the one that best brings together the capable elements of reconciling theory with practice. Reading is an extremely complex act, because it represents a decoding process that mobilizes memory, the epistemic set to which the individual has access. Finally, it is concluded that the theme addressed about the act of reading, as part of the process of human epistemological development, must be analyzed in the rational light of phylogeny and ontogeny, because the human being, at birth, is a blank board, being, only endowed with the ability to develop the neurological processes that will enable and enhance the condition of resourcefulness in the acts of reading and understanding what has been read.

Keywords: Act of reading; Reading; writing.

INTRODUCTION

All human action is loaded with symbolism and understanding needs, as well as decoding needs for these elements. Specifically, with regard to the act of reading, questions arise that challenge scientific understanding, because, paraphrasing Saint Augustine of Hippo

(430-354) in his reference to time ¹³, if no one questions what the act of reading means and/or represents, it can be seen that all unanimously know what he is, means, or represents; however, it is enough to do like Socrates and carry out a simple question that discovers that everyone, in a [*almost*] unanimous way, does not know what he means and/or represents.

Reading is an act of extreme complexity, because, as it represents a decoding process that mobilizes memory, the epistemic set to which the individual has access, and this involves a whole range of words, expressions, jargon, a lexical system that, together the prior knowledge of each student enables the understanding and expression of the symbols (words) represented.

This article addresses an open and clear question about the act of reading, in which it seeks to know what it actually represents? This could be a strange question, were it not for the historical moment in which they are all located, in the West, being able to say that we are a civilization that expresses itself through spelling and communicates through this symbolic instrument, and that, for that, so that there is an efficient understanding between the communicating parties, most of the time using monologues, that is, through the reading of a monologue, written at a different time, read at another time, in which the interpreter is the reader himself.

This unique condition transforms the act of reading into an act of analysis, which can unfold into semantic analysis, textual analysis, linguistic analysis, contextual analysis and beyond that, into an interpretive, deductive act, reaching the apex of being a comprehensive act, which allows the adaptation of the being to its space, to its historical, political and social time. When viewed from this conjunctural perspective, the act of reading is one of the most complex mechanisms that human beings have ever invented and that cannot be learned without the support of a duly prepared tutor, contrary to Arthur Schopenhauer (1788). -1860) who defended the idea that learning to read is a mechanical act that anyone can learn on their own.

In order to read a text, regardless of the dimension of its complexity, the reader must mobilize a whole chain of mnemonic thoughts and compare them with each other. First, you must know the letters and phonemes; must know how to systematically join simple and complex syllables to form words and how to pronounce them; must know their meanings within the context expressed, because otherwise, one is not performing an act of reading, but a mechanical decoding of cultural symbols. In addition to all this, you must know how to inflect your voice when reading so that the text makes sense in its grammatical structure. Breathing control, the pressure placed on the diaphragm so that the sound comes out in the right tone for the listeners

¹³In this regard read: SAINT AUGUSTINE. *Confessions*. Sao Paulo: Martin Claret, 2004.

and the textual writing. Even if it is a silent reading, all these elements must be respected and executed so that the text read does not lose its semantic or epistemological meaning.

The act of reading represents the desire to know something that escapes knowledge; it may be that the reader wants to relax and then uses this technique to achieve his goal, but the human brain is always in search of a type of pleasure that, when achieved, causes pleasant sensations and then generates the need for the act to be repeated. When a scientist focuses on readings, his end is already given, he wants to discover essential components that help him to explain the phenomenon investigated; this would allow us to deduce that the act of reading is a type of scientific research. And beyond the scientist, there is the student who aims to achieve the necessary knowledge to be approved and also to become a qualified and competent professional.

The fact that the human being was the only species to develop the capacity for language, which allowed him the ability to speak, does not mean that reading precedes the acquisition of knowledge about the elements that compose it; this is the same as admitting that human beings think before they exist. As René Descarte himself (1596-1650) admits, existence precedes essence (2000); Thus, human beings develop all the neurological capacity of speech articulation and then, if products are provided that help them to interpret the cultural symbols expressed in a graphic way, they will be able to read and express them, through orality, verbalizing -you.

To

Considering reading as a process of understanding formal and symbolic expressions , no matter what language, [...] the act of reading refers both to something written and to other types of expression of human doing, characterizing it also as a historical event and establishing an equally historical relationship between the reader and what is read (MARTINS, 1988, p. 30).

From this it can be inferred that, when reading, the individual immerses himself in history, seeking to decipher it, in his own way, having his own time, his ability to read and what has been conditioned as an epistemological basis.

In an attempt to achieve its goal, the reader needs to mobilize several areas of his brain that can cause him joy, sadness, apathy or pain. This is a very complex biological neurochemical process, which provides conditions for cognitive and intellectual maturity as the stages linked to the child's age progress.

READING AND MEMORY

Reading and memory are two mental constructs that always go together and there is no way to be otherwise, because reading is a process of interpretation (decoding) of something that refers to the past, subordinated to the semantic field of remembrance. The equation is not difficult to synthesize because, for an individual to describe the symbols, he must have known them, made a systemic and epistemic contact with them, at a previous moment, which allows him to say that he knows, that is, he was taught, therefore, he learned.

The concept of reading, in its broad dimensions, is restricted to the deciphering of codes that are created by humanity and some that are classified and automatically receive denominations that, *a posteriori*, lead to a need for interpretation by those who succeed, to what inflicted the symbolic character to the object. However, reading goes beyond a mere interpretation of signs, because it refers to an exercise, which requires knowledge, mastery of a technique, practice in the act and fluency in execution.

Human memory has the ability to preserve traces of past experience and to evoke it in order to make use of it in the present and in the future, according to the unique need of each individual. For man, memories should disappear, because this is one of the functions of forgetting, protecting the individual's mental health, allowing an equitable balance of his psychic economy. The best characterized concept of memory is that presented by José Lino Bueno, where he states that “memory is a set of procedures that allows us to manipulate and understand the world, taking into account the current context and individual experiences, recreating this world through of actions of the imagination” (BUENO, 1977, p. 36), allowing to reach an understanding that it is, perhaps, for this reason that nature has endowed it with a spontaneous condition of manipulation by the human brain about what will be forgotten and /or remembered.

In this, we have that once you learn to read, you don't forget it anymore, because this is a common practice in a literate world. However, we enter into a paradox, because the ability to read, once acquired, is not lost, because it is a neurological acquisition, in which a whole set of synapses is formed, which remain there, until death, however, , the lack of contact with the language and with the linguistic expressions can favor forgetting the way of pronunciation of certain words and the sounds referring to them.

In acquiring the practice of reading and its respective mastery, many techniques must be employed, in order to ensure that it meets the necessary harmony requirements. As an example of this, there is the question of the orality of certain words, others are of nasal tone,

the movements that the tongue must make inside the mouth so that it is reproduced in the correct timbre and in the original format of expression of the word read. Then, constant exercises must be carried out so that all this linguistic construction is properly stored in memory, to be used at opportune times.

As in human beings, everything has to be taught, even what some theorists call *reading the world*, is *a priori* taught to children and they keep the mnemonic precepts, mobilizing them when they deem relevant for their own interpretations of reality. The child has what can be called concrete intelligence, one that is conditioned to a not so refined interpretation of the problems that affect him and it is only after puberty that he begins to delineate the first objective traits of abstract intelligence, forming what Vygotsky (1896-1934) called *higher mental processes*¹⁴. For this author, literacy (understood as the abstract ability to read and interpret the real) represents the culmination of a historical process of differentiation in the use of mediating instruments (VYGOTSKY, 2000).

For children, the act of reading represents enormous power, independence, freedom, a feeling of power, because it keeps in their memories the moments when their parents *read* to them, since they still did not master such a task, or even, because he watched his father leaf through the books and the newspaper, pausing for hours on end to decipher. This, for them, represents a mystery to be unraveled, because what fantastic things are contained in those elements that are able to hold the attention of adults for so long?!

This finding highlights the importance of memory both for life and for the [*practice*] of reading. Mainly the [*reading*] of the written word – the appreciation of knowing how to read and write – since it is an arbitrary sign, not available in nature, created as an instrument of communication, a record of human relationships, actions and aspirations of men (MARTINS, 1988, p. 19).

In the sense given by the author, about the act of reading, it represents the way through which the current generation becomes aware of and makes contact with everything that their ancestors created, thought and imagined for themselves and their descendants. Through this domain, they can reproduce the past, understand it and project ideals into the future and it is when they take possession of this type of understanding that they become holders of power, the

¹⁴LS Vygotsky categorized as *higher mental processes*, cognitive and intellectual attitudes referring to “ processes of mastery of the external means of cultural development and thought: language, writing, calculation, drawing; and, to processes of development of special higher psychic functions, not limited or precisely determined, which in traditional psychology is called voluntary attention, logical memory, formation of concepts, etc. Both, taken together, form what we conventionally qualify as processes of development of higher forms of student conduct” (VYGOTSKY, 2000c, p. 29). **Source:** VYGOTSKY, Lev Semenovitch. *The social formation of mind*. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2000c.

true will to power is born. So it is not the act of reading that confers power; it is the ability to read, understand and know how to act on the given problems with the due wisdom acquired through readings. Here, we have a representation of the act of reading in the Immanuel Kant style, in which the mastery of reading, the act of reading, represents the departure of man from his condition of minority, the victory of reason over his instincts, because it makes it possible to be human reach enlightenment.

READING AND WRITING

Reading and writing are terms that started to walk together, after the 19th century, not being an objective reality until this moment in history, even though Western society could already be considered a graphotechnical civilization. This fact, in particular, is due to *the Industrial Revolution*, which generated needs for more qualified labor, drastically changing the teaching and learning modes. There was a distinction between those who mastered the technique of writing and those who mastered the reading of graphic symbols.

In Antiquity, before writing appeared, there was no need or possibility for someone to know how to read or write, and in this regard, meticulous care must be taken in the approach, because, the fact that priests and rural men, perform the interpretations of signs of nature such as religious manifestations and signs of forecasts for rains, droughts, storms, harvests, floods of rivers, can already be understood as a form of reading. But it is not this aspect that this essay is about, and it should focus on the linguistic interpretation of symbols created by man himself, in order to promote the communication, *a posteriori*, of his ideas, plans, strategies, commercial goods, stories, etc. .

Thus, the creation of writing preceded the practice of reading. It is no enigma to be deciphered, because, first, men created the symbols and then gave them meanings, and from this intellectual elaboration, it allowed the emergence of the cognitive elaboration in which another individual would be taught how to understand the meaning of those elements expressed on the surfaces and, once this is done, wherever this interpreter arrives and comes across such symbols, he would know how to read them, being able to teach others the technique.

This unique condition conferred by the mastery of the writing and reading technique meant that certain precautions were taken by the kings of antiquity, such as teaching one the art of writing and the other the art of reading; never to both the two techniques. In this mode, the scribe only knew how to write what was dictated to him by the king and the reader only knew how to read the parchments when requested by his superior.

This is an issue that divides opinion among academics, because it is possible that someone learns to read and not learn to write; however, those who learn to write also learn to read, because they exercise different and equitable areas of the brain at the same time; but this was something that went unnoticed by the kings and sages of antiquity and has reached our days as an absolute truth.

Reading and writing were not always synonymous with elevated *status quo*. Historically, writing traces its origins to a time approximately 7000 years before our era. At that time, writing and reading, literacy did not form part of a hierarchy within a process of social evolution, since they simply did not exist. In Egypt, it was very difficult to get children and young people who wanted to follow a career as a scribe, because this meant poverty, belonging to the lower class and even in Classical Antiquity, Middle Ages (High and Low) and until the 18th century, the great kings, most nobles and knights, statesmen, were illiterate. They posed for great artists in the midst of many books, because this represented a sign of ostentation and power; however, mastering the technique of writing and reading was a sign of social depreciation.

William Shakespeare ¹⁵(1564-1616) was an author who put into the mouths of his characters the contempt for the art of reading and writing and the governor of the State of Virginia, in the 18th century, was proud of not having schools of first letters in his State, nor presses ¹⁶, which he pejoratively called *paper mills*.

The reading activity gains *status* from the creation of the press by Guttenberg ¹⁷. From this event onwards, a greater volume of publications began to appear which, even though they still had a very high cost, already had a drastic reduction in relation to the production by papyrus and parchment. Then came the age of the book and, automatically, it became necessary for there to be readers to consume them.

Another leap that marked the history of reading was with the *Protestant Revolution* (1517), in which Martin Luther (1483-1546) wanted all men to be able to read the Bible. This generates another type of need, singular, the people should be literate, regardless of their social class. The criticisms that emerged around that this possession of the ability to read was restricted to a miserable condition of understanding, not providing deeper levels of exploration of the universe of understanding that was taken possession of through the act of reading, cannot be considered as worthy of legitimacy, because the improvement of the ability to read and interpret

¹⁵Read Shakespeare's *Henry VIII*.

¹⁶In this regard, read: SOUZA, SR *Ethics and its attributes: a psychoanalytic perspective*. São Paulo: PerSe, 2016.

¹⁷In this regard, read: POSTMAN, Neil. *The Disappearance of Childhood*. Rio de Janeiro: Grafhia Editorial, 1999.

is a subjective act, which the individual has to want for himself and be willing to pay a high price for it and we do not refer to monetary values, but rather the acceptance of analysis, the ability to abstract beyond your horizons, the experience with other cultural models, which may provide you with more or less clear visions of the world that surrounds you.

These two historical events [*cited above*] profoundly marked changes in the habits of societies, introducing the habit of reading as an essential component of human life, culminating in the legal act of understanding literacy [*understood as the ability to read and write fluently*] as a subjective public right of a social nature, that is, illiteracy can no longer be a present reality in society. Therefore, literacy can be considered as a social practice that, in the current model of society, has become an essential domain tool for the correct insertion of the individual in the environment. The literacy process can be defined as what people do with their reading and writing skills, in the social context in which they work and how these skills relate to social needs, values and practices, and may consider the practice of acquisition. of literacy as a form of adaptation to the environment, a form of social inclusion.

Characterizing the reading conceptions Maria Helena Martins (1988) reveals that,

The numerous current conceptions of *reading, roughly speaking*, can be summarized in two characterizations: 1) as a mechanical decoding of linguistic signs, through learning established from stimulus-response conditioning (behaviorist-Skinnerian perspective); 2) as a process of comprehensive understanding, whose dynamics involves sensory, emotional, intellectual, physiological, neurological, as well as cultural, economic and political components (cognitive-sociological perspective) (MARTINS, 1988, p. 31).

This interpretation about the act of reading presented by the author is, too, simple and devoid of an analytical sense considering the phylogenetic and ontogenetic prism, because, during the childhood phase, teaching has to be provided in a mechanical way, since that the little ones still do not have the neurological and cognitive maturity minimally necessary to perform cognitive and/or mnemonic abstractions.

From the moment it advances in the processes of synaptic production and evolves to highly elaborated levels of cognition, it starts to appropriate the instruments that allow it to reach the stages of comprehensive understanding referred to by the aforementioned author, creating more refined objectives. of application to the gnosiological elements. Education systems, as well as teachers and those responsible for the education of children, adolescents and young people must remain attentive to increase the load of linguistic challenges at each stage overcome by the student, so that their reading ability is always improving, until reaching the level of excellence.

And so it should be, because in the conception of Fabrício Silveira (2017), the act of reading has the power to give life to written elements, which otherwise would be retained on the surface of the paper without expressing what he felt he wanted to express. author, when he put the words on the paper. This author understands that,

To read is to take possession of the text to endow it with existence, since every readable sign opens up to infinite possibilities of meaning. Not by chance, every reader has the power to unveil a truth that is not transparent, but latent, potentially present, hidden outside consciousness, immanent, singular and, until then, inexpressible (SILVEIRA, 2017, p. 5).

Thus understood, writing has expanded the dream of communication, however, it was the ability to decode this model of artificial symbols that allowed it to gain a concrete tone, giving life to the object of the symbolic exchange of messages. It was Saint Thomas Aquinas who stated that words have transcendental power, given that they can be read at very extensive temporal distances and still provoke astonishment, awaken different emotions and feelings in those who read them, transmitting lucid messages, endowed with a timeless power.

None of this makes sense [*or if it does, it will have very little impact*], if the reader is not gifted with the ability to interpret the symbols respecting their original orality, rhetoric, if they do not possess the capacity for eloquence that gives life and meaning to what is being read. Therefore, it is not enough to know how to read, it is necessary to know the history of each text, the grammatical rules and, at the very least, each textual genre, so that the act of reading does not become an act of rhetorical murder, contrary to the expectation exposed above. that the act of reading gives life to what is read. This is a subject raised by Martins (1988) [*cited above*], in which, first of all, the teaching of the act of reading is something mechanical, based on the theory of reinforcement and the consolidation of its learning takes place through repetition, here being in agreement with Aristotle of Stagira (384 BC-322 BC), adding that, as the act is repeated, the negative results must be discarded and/or corrected; the positive results already achieved were valued and new challenges were posed to improve the technique.

This condition given to reading, as having the power to give life to the text, is an arbitrary demarcation, because from a finer analytical perspective, how reading is performed is consistent with how the acceptance and interpretation of the text will be, even because all the life inserted and inferred in a text is in the narrator's utterance, in the *quantum of pathos* that he manages to add to his oratory. Therefore, it is not just a matter of knowing how to read, it is implied how to read and how to read, considering that each work, in particular, has its original singular *ethos* , which was conferred on it by its creator.

In this discussion parameter, about reading, Adler and Van Doren (1954) are forceful in stating that,

The demarcation line between how to read and how to read is often blurred. As long as we keep the two kinds of reading distinct, we can use this word in two different senses. The first refers to reading newspapers, magazines or anything else that is immediately understandable (...). It may increase our store of knowledge, but it does not improve our understanding, which has not changed since we started. The second meaning refers to the reading of something that, at first glance, was not fully understood (ADLER and VAN DOREN, 1954, p. 20),

Therefore, it needs new readings and, sometimes, complementary readings so that the etymological, epistemological and gnosiological meanings of terms, ideas, theories and expressions can become as transparent as possible to the reader. The more complex the reading, the less the individual's desire to read, because this does not bring him pleasure; the emotions provoked are those of discomfort and incapacity.

THE READING AND THE SQUARATIC FUNCTION OF BRUNNER'S DISTANCE

Jerome Seymour Brunner (1915-2016), in partnership with his Psychology students, arrived at a denominator on the issue of the dimension of the object projected in the human mind, which, for this result, he called *Brunner's Quadratic Distance Function*. It is a quantitative value that the size of an object represented in the human mind is equivalent to the inverse square of the distance between the observed object and the observer (BRUNNER, 1975).

This discovery caught the scientist's attention due to the fact that the further away he is from the object, the greater the possibilities of being able to see it in its entirety, and with reading it could not be otherwise, because the older it is, the older it is. distant in time, the texts to be read, the greater the conditions for the analysis to be more faithful, because it is possible to see, in greater amplitude, the analyzed object and the radius of observation of its context.

This is an idea to which the social psychologist Gustave Le Bon (1841-1931) would have great objections, because in his conception one cannot trust the criteria of human judgment that are betrayed by their senses even at close range. However, one thing is a reading of a visual fact, an event in which one is an eyewitness, being under strong impression, pressure, etc. syntax application.

In this sense, the greater the distance, the more transparent the reader's relationship of understanding with the object becomes, because reading is a total act, in which the agent

mobilizes a whole range of feelings and artifacts that will help him/her in the execution of his/her task. enterprise. Therefore, in this aspect, the act of reading represents the possibility of shedding light on the past, clarifying it, making it more objective and in tune with the present.

When the act of reading allows the individual a glimpse, it is at this moment [*not to say, moment*] that it becomes a political act, because it provides the ability to make a critical reading of the environment that surrounds him and that shaped him. Let us understand the *critical expression* in the precept of Kantian thought that it is a public question addressed to any object that can be analyzed and answered, without constraints for the parties involved, that is, it is about the domain of knowledge about to *believe that you know* .

Thus, the act of reading promotes the freedom to find the answer to problems, by itself, providing conditions of autonomy beyond what the individual had even imagined possible. This is a role that is given to the basic education school with greater emphasis, because the child remains in their space for approximately a decade and a half, therefore, it is inadmissible that they reach the end of this period without complete mastery of the act of reading, in all areas that can be addressed. And with each passing year in the academic-school environment, it distances itself more from the world that preceded it, making, automatically, its condition of interpretation and understanding of the past, more accurate and with greater power of rhetoric and linguistic expression on the objects chosen for scientific studies.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In order to consider the theme treated about the act of reading, this process must be analyzed in the rational light of phylogeny and ontogeny, because the human being, at birth, is a blank table, being, only endowed with the ability to develop the neurological processes that will enable and enhance the condition of resourcefulness in the acts of reading and understanding what has been read.

Thus, the act of reading begins with the absorption of simple contents, which are, little by little, archived in memory and which, given the needs of application on the reality of each one, are mobilized, according to the cognitive capacity. of each individual and these contents become complex, by themselves, as the potential for knowledge of each one matures until being able to decode texts of high complexity, symbols of greater expressions, all this within the space of epistemic knowledge. -cultural of each one.

To carry out the reading activity, the individual needs to know the parts that make up each word in particular, from vowels, consonants, simple syllables, complex syllables, reaching

the point of being able to consider themselves literate, a fact that at each level of education makes it is more demanded that the reader learns and apprehends the contents pertinent to the reading and to the learning potential of the reading expression.

Reading is not an act of pleasure for children, and the answer is obvious and simple: it prevents them from playing with things that really provoke pleasure. Children are the closest form to a mental-cognitive model of prehistoric man; thus, all the things that to adults seem to be of extreme relevance, to them are innocuous, insipid and without the slightest sense. As it grows, creating new synaptic structures, involving in the social sphere, in which other demands and social needs arise, as part of the human developmental process, the taste for reading is emerging and being expanded, until it becomes a habit. . This involves other neurological instances, such as endocrinological processes, production of hormones that will characterize the act of reading as an act of pleasure.

This part of the psychobiological development of the human being, linked to the act of reading, is a field of Neurology that needs further study, because when a child is forced to read and he/she rebels and ends up turning pages violently, the hormone produced is the cortisol, which is responsible for the production of *stress* . On the other hand, when he assumes the act of reading as an activity that awakens him to the fantastic, he starts producing endorphins, which are a pleasure hormone.

In this, we have that the act of reading is an activity that is not only complete, but also complex, because it mobilizes an entire history of human potential, ranging from the most basic academic and school education to the highest level of scientific education. At each stage of development, new challenges arise that can cause *stress*, given the difficulties of overcoming them, and which, at the same time, can be provoking pleasure, once the difficulties are overcome.

The allegory that children acquire reading habits because their parents read texts, stories and other anecdotes to them, even while they were in their mother's womb and/or while they were small, are beliefs that are not justified. One can start by understanding how the idea came about that a child can hear something while still in the mother's womb. The ear is the only organ of the senses that, when the child is born, is already fully developed, from the sixth month of life, that is, even before birth. However, Physics has already proven that sound does not propagate in a liquid medium and the baby is immersed in a placenta loaded with amniotic fluid, so it is impossible for the baby to hear the stories told by the mother. What supposedly happens is that this habit produces endorphins for the mother, which automatically produces

relaxation and comfort for her, reflecting on the condition of the child's embryonic development.

Reading is a habit and children copy their parents' habits, following the Vygotskian maxim that the best advice for a child is the good example of the parents. Thus, children who have the habit of reading from an early age is because their parents have such a habit, with ample personal libraries at home. Therefore, reading stories to children at bedtime does not contribute to their acquisition of the reading habit.¹⁸

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¹⁸In this regard, read: *Freaknomics* : The hidden side of everything that affects us.